

SEVEN INSIGHTS FOR VIETNAM'S POWER SECTOR ENERGY TRANSITION

Position paper

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About Vietnam Initiative for Energy Transition

The Vietnam Initiative for Energy Transition (VIET) is a newly established research and advocacy think tank specialized on the energy transition. It assembles a team of Vietnamese analysts to examine the factors enabling a fast and affordable energy transition in Vietnam. The Vietnam Initiative for Energy Transition is not affiliated with an academy, institute, university, company or ministry. VIETSE is funded by philanthropic foundations and consulting work.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Examining the factors enabling a fast and affordable energy transition in Vietnam in the power sector, we found seven insights related to the feasibility of a massive penetration of carbon-free technologies in the electricity mix. These propositions renew the narrative on energy in the country, compared to the current discourse on how to provide energy security, ensure access for everyone and protect the environment.

1. The next Power Development Plan 8 is the historical opportunity to chart the way towards a low-carbon power system and avoid locking Vietnam in a high carbon society.
2. Increasing efficiency in energy supply and demand benefits economic growth.
3. Solar and wind electricity generation costs are competitive with those of fossil fuels.
4. Renewable energy targets will be achieved and can be increased with proper policies. The world is installing more new solar and wind power generation capacity than new coal power generation capacity, and this can happen in Vietnam too in the next few years because project developers are quick to follow the Government's incentives.
5. Solar and wind electric system integration now is the time to solve it.
6. Power market reforms are necessary to attract investment in energy sources, and private capital prefers renewable energy sources.
7. Power from gas is cleaner but does not resolve the energy security issue.

Table of Contents

	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
	Introduction	4
Insight 1. Power Development Plan 8 can chart Vietnam's way to a low carbon power system		5
	Insight 2. Increase energy efficiency benefits economic growth	7
Insight 3. Solar and wind electricity generation costs are competitive with those of fossil fuels		9
Insight 4. Renewable energy targets will be achieved and can be increased with proper policies		11
	Insight 5. Solar and wind electric system integration: now is the time to solve it	13
Insight 6. Power market reforms are necessary to attract investment in additional capacity		15
	Insight 7. Power from gas is cleaner but does not resolve the energy security issue	17
	Towards a new energy narrative	20
	References	21

Introduction

The power source development trajectory in 7th Power Development Plan (PDP 7A) with the dominance of coal would be expired in a year. The PDP 8 currently under preparation for 2020 will define how Vietnam moves towards a lower carbon and more sustainable future. There are motivations and challenges for the energy transition in Vietnam.

1. Challenges: The energy demand is increasing with demographic expansion, economic growth, and industrialization. Renewable energy facilities require high investment costs, which exceed the local financing capacity. Much remain to be done to improve the governance, regarding for example official data & statistics, the legal frameworks or reform to have all levels of competitive electricity markets. Discussions on long term policy goals are hard to stabilize and close, as fast development imply that master plans must be revised deep and often.
2. Motivations: In the last two decades, the government has found ways to reform and restructure many sectors in the economic system, making Vietnam a development success story. Local air pollution levels makes checking the development of coal power plant a visible necessity. The risk of power shortage is back due to delays in building power plants. The domestic fossil fuels production capacities are insufficient to provide for the domestic demand, while sun and wind abounds. Exposure to international coal price risk since 2016. Foreign capital is flowing into solar and wind investment projects.

The energy transition requires a lot of smart thinking and social dialogue, especially in high economic growth and industrializing countries. In this report, we introduce seven insights to prove that a massive penetration of carbon-free technologies in the electricity mix is possible and propose a few steps towards the implementation of green growth in power sector.

Insight 1

Power Development Plan 8 can chart Vietnam's way to a low carbon power system

The words Energy Transition mean “a deep change in the way a society produces and uses energy”. The world has experienced two energy transitions: wood-to-coal and coal-to-oil. The current transition is from fossil fuels to renewable and carbon neutral energy sources. While the past energy transitions were mostly market-driven, the current move towards solar and wind is mostly policy-driven. Greenhouse gases emission reduction policies has been adopted to lessen the risks of climate change. Many countries and cities aim at carbon neutrality by 2050 (Ardern and Heine, 2018). One of the most important targets of climate policies is the power sector, in which a worldwide shift toward low carbon power systems is being observed.

Vietnam's power sector also experienced dramatically change in term of primary sources. Figure 1 shows the three transitions of primary source for electricity generation in Vietnam. Each transition happens in less than two decades. 1) Between 1975 to 2000, electricity production capacity development was mostly about hydropower. 2) From 2000 to 2010, natural gas was at the forefront. 3) Since 2010 coal has got momentum to become the dominant source of power generation. As Figure 1 shows, the PDP7 revised planned to push this momentum further.

Figure 1. Vietnam installed (pre 2015) and registered (according to PDP7 revised) power generation capacity (GW) by technology. (Ha-Duong and Nguyen-Trinh, 2017)

Historical development of Vietnam's power system indicates that its structure can change rapidly. There is still an option to avoid a lock-in of fossil-fuels based power generation system, but the window of opportunity is closing rapidly. The eight Power Development Plan is scheduled to be approved by the end of 2020. It has to be the one starting the energy transition towards a low carbon electricity generation system, or it will be too late.

We propose that the highest political body in Vietnam gives time targets directives to the government, to make action of its statements to “Not develop more coal power” (Prime Minister Nguyen Tan Dung, 2016), and to “minimize coal-fired thermal power, especially old-fashioned technology” (Prime Minister Nguyen Xuan Phuc, Hau Giang, 2017/09/28).

We propose that PDP8 abandons all (new) coal projects planned in the PDP7A that do not have an investor, a location or a realistic scheduled completion date. This would imply that the PDP8 introduce significantly less coal power in 2030 than currently foreseen in the PDP7A.

Insight 2

Increase energy efficiency benefits economic growth

Vietnam has enormous untapped energy efficiency potential. This is another way to say that little energy efficiency improvements have been observed in the last twenty years, compared to other countries. Vietnam was one of the most energy intensive economies in the world in 2014 (VNEEP, 2017, fig. 6). Comparatively speaking, Vietnam's economic output contains relatively more energy intensive goods. But we argue that the macro-economic structure is not the only reason. Most industry sectors have opportunities to catch up with international standards in energy efficiency.

The Vietnam Energy Efficiency Program (VNEEP I) ran from 2006 to 2010 and VNEEP II ran from 2011 to 2015 contributed to a 3.4% and 5.6% energy efficiency improvement. After a 5 years gap, the VNEEP III is designed to achieve an efficiency gain of 8 – 10% per total national commercial energy consumption for 2019-2030 (Rainer Brohm, 2018). This is less ambitious than Resolution at the Congress of the XII National Communist Party to reduce energy consumption per unit of GDP by 1 – 1.5% per year (Pham Hoang Mai, 2017). This is also lower than the global energy intensity reduction rate, which was above 1.7% this decade according to Joe Ritchie et al. (2018).

Faster progress is required if Vietnam is not to remain one of the world's most energy inefficient economies. The urgency is recognized in the Vietnam's Green Growth strategy, which aimed to reduce elasticity of electricity/GDP from 2.0 in 2012 to 1.0 in the year 2020 (Prime Minister, 2012 para 9.b.1). In the long run, the competitive economies are those who produce the most value using the least resources.

The path to go forward is well defined, with five components that have to be procured at the same time, to build a whole ecosystem across the economy:

- Norms and regulations with incitation. Evidence-based norms can be based on energy performance benchmark studies for each industry sector, as UNIDO did for the steel industry (Joe Herbertson and Chu Duc Khai, 2011) for example.
- An industry of energy service companies (ESCOs) who are technically able to audit factories / buildings, prescribe cost-effective energy saving measures, help implement them, and take contractual responsibility for the result.
- Financing mechanisms for energy saving investments.
- Energy efficiency and conservation national information systems. The existing provincial data from the Designated Energy Users program could be merged in a more comprehensive Vietnam Energy Information System.
- Capacity building, education and research. Establish university training programs in Energy Auditing and Management that lead to internationally recognized certifications levels.

We propose to switch the incitation strategy from sticks to carrots. Compliance ensuring mechanisms have been ineffective, they cannot be enforced until there are practical ways for industries to comply. Energy efficiency help and rewards are more likely to grow the ecosystem.

Insight 3

Solar and wind electricity generation costs are competitive with those of fossil fuels

Costs of renewable energy system around the world are decreasing, so if the economic competitiveness of wind and solar was debatable in 2016, the question is settled in 2020. In international market conditions, the financial costs of power generation from renewable energy sources (wind and solar) are comparable to the financial costs of power generation from conventional fossil fuels sources (coal and gas) (Lazard, 2018). In Vietnam, the technical costs of renewable energy systems are also falling (see Figure 2). However, beyond the technical costs of the production system, generating electricity involves remunerating work, land and capital; paying for fuels; and bearing with polluting emissions. There are many viewpoints on costs at play in technology choices beyond the technical costs.

The location determines the resources availability, this is why most coal power plants are in the North of Vietnam, while most solar, wind and gas power plants are in the South. The location also determines the cost of connecting to the electricity transmission network, which may be large for solar and wind farms developed in remote areas. Projects risks and therefore capital costs increase with size and lead time, but decrease with technology and investment environment maturity. The risk of stranded assets is lower with renewables power plants, because they do not depend on

Figure 2. Cost of electricity by technologies using data from the Vietnam Technology Catalogue (Jakob Lundsager, Nguyen Ngoc Hung and Mikael Togeby, 2019). Costs of utility scale solar PV and wind are expected to be reduced in the future. The error bars show the variation of fuel price over 60 years of observation by International Energy Agency from 1960 – 2015. Source: VIET.

future climate policy and fossil fuels markets. PV power production costs are below 9.35 cents / kWh in Vietnam, and some PV projects in other countries benefiting from favorable location, time schedule and capital conditions have been realized under 4 cents / kWh.

From the provincial perspective, while renewables – especially solar - use more land area, fossil fuels – especially coal - have higher environmental impact on air and water. This has led some southern provinces to remove coal plants projects from their development plan. Bac Lieu and Long An provinces are rejecting the central plans for coal plants (VNS, 2018). In both cases, the plans switched to gas-based generation. The government of Vietnam recognized the external costs of fossil fuel-based energy through the establishment of environment tax on coal. However, the full costs of local pollution are not yet passed on to coal-based electricity production in Vietnam. Air quality standards are currently less stringent than in other ASEAN countries.

From international community perspective, using coal is incompatible with the climate protection. One way to see it is through the social value of carbon. If it were 50 USD/tCO₂, since producing 1 MWh from coal emits about 1 t of CO₂ then the carbon cost of coal electricity is 5 UScent/kWh. This is the same order of magnitude as the market price of electricity in Vietnam. It explains why so many development partners are actively engaged for less carbon intensive Vietnam energy system.

The development of renewables brings additional macroeconomic benefits. It reduces the import of fossil fuels, resulting in a positive impact on national trade balance and a potential release of international diplomacy constraints. Access to reliable electricity spurs development, facilitating education and business achievements in remote areas. Jobs created directly in the power sector create more jobs indirectly in the local community around them.

We propose that independent domestic expertise capacity be built for the PDP8 impact assessment to ensure that the PDP8: Makes an efficient use of national resources; Cohere with the Vietnam's Renewable Energy Development Strategy; Complies with the Nationally Determined Commitments to the Paris Agreement; and Contributes to respecting national air quality norms everywhere.

Insight 4

Renewable energy targets will be achieved and can be increased with proper policies

Starting from negligible levels in 2016, wind and solar power generation in Vietnam has entered a phase of exponential growth: incentives to attract investors worked (Nguyễn Xuân Phúc, 2017). For example the Government commanded EVN to buy solar PV electricity at 2 086 VND/kWh for projects completed before mid-2019. The market price of electricity wholesale is most of the time below 1 200 VND/kWh. The incentive has been generous to developers, and they noticed.

The solar power industry already achieved the PDP 7A's target for 2020 (Figure 3) with 25 solar power projects commissioned for a total installed capacity of 1 406 MW by 15 May 2019 (National Load Dispatch Center, 2019). 6 weeks later, EVN has done an incredible job of connecting another 3 000 MW of solar capacity to the grid to help Vietnam power system surpass 2025 target of 4 000 MW of solar power by the end of June 2019.

Wind power capacity in operation by August 2019 was 346 MW, with 990 MW in construction, 160 MW had groundbreaking and 3 545 MW approved (Ha-Duong and Teske, 2019). Logistics for wind projects are heavier than for solar projects, 12-24 months construction times. Hence, expecting that most of the sites under construction or groundbreaking in Spring 2019 will be completed before the end of 2020 is reasonable. The wind power industry will reach the plan objectives of 800 MW around the end of 2020.

The renewable power industry is on track to meet the plan objectives for 2025, but several conditions are required to sustain the growth beyond the initial rush. Owning and operating a PV farm is riskier in Vietnam than in most other contexts. This is because the standard power purchase agreement (PPA) protects the buyer (EVN) more than the seller (the PV farm). EVN may not take the electricity and pay if there is a technical problem, for example transmission lines congestion. The contract may be terminated unilaterally early with a compensation of only one year of sales. And conflict resolution is not by international arbitration but in Vietnam. Because of these, the first wave of PV farms in Vietnam was financed by domestic banks, and international banks stayed out. The successful operation of the current wave of projects can reduce the perceived risk and demonstrate the business case for renewable energy in Vietnam. If the risks are lowered, investors might be able to access cheaper capital, from international private banks.

Figure 3. Timeline of solar power project commissioning shows the exponential growth of the industry. In July 2018 the capacity was too thin to see on the graph. By May 2019, the total capacity of solar power projects in operation is higher than PDP 7A target for 2020. Installed solar capacity already exceeded the 2025 target by the end of June 2019.

We propose to increase the 2025 renewable energy targets above those of the Renewable Energy Development Strategy, given that the PDP7A goals have been reached early.

We propose to support the development of bioenergy through a renewable energy portfolio standard. Electricity generated from biomass can provide some flexibility to the system. In many countries, when electricity producers have been required to source a minimum fraction their production from renewable sources, thermal power plants started to co-fire biomass as a substitute for fossil fuels.

We propose to consider technology-neutral auction mechanisms in order to procure electricity. The next step to allow for auctions mechanisms is to revise both the Vietnam Electricity Law (chapters IV, VI & IX) and the Investment Law (or its Decree No. 118/2015/ND-CP).

Insight 5

Solar and wind electric system integration: now is the time to solve it

Satisfying the demand for electricity with variable renewables generation remains an important technical challenge in the energy transition. For example, solar farms generate most power during the afternoon. This pattern fits well with the afternoon peak in Vietnam due to air conditioning. But other sources have to be called in the early evening, when the electricity consumption is still high. Pescia (2019) and IEA (2017) asserts that solar and wind energy integration in the electric system should be addressed in successive phases.

1. Variable renewables (i.e. wind and solar) are not relevant at the all-system level when they represent less than 2-3% of electricity production. The challenges depend mainly on the local conditions of the grid. Renewable generation hotspots may call for reinforcement of the distribution grid in some region. Indeed, curtailments happened in July 2017 in Ninh Thuan and Binh Thuan, two renewable generation hotspots. National Load Dispatch Center had to regulate the amount of electricity that PV farms can inject to grid to avoid congestion.
2. As the share of variable renewable energy sources increase, their impact becomes noticeable by the system operator. Developments in real time dispatching technology and market structures, planning and clever incentives become key. Hung and Togeby (2019, pp. 23–24) show that wind and solar could satisfy 12% of the annual power demand in 2030, without major change in the variability of the system, using only about 2 GW of battery storage for the whole country and balancing the intra-day variability with hydroelectricity. On top of solving more grid hotspot issues, operational practices must be changed. This is where Vietnam is in mid – 2019 when intermittent renewable share in production capacity is about 8%.
3. When variable renewable energy sources are above about 15% of the electricity supply, the challenges depends mainly on the availability of flexible resources: smart grid based demand side management, large scale battery storage, pumped hydro storage, interconnecting with neighboring countries, retrofitting the thermal power plants to increase their flexibility. Innovative technologies such as concentrated solar power with storage, flywheels, compressed air storage, smart vehicle to grid will be relevant. The challenges of grid stability (inertia, voltage stability) comes only with even higher shares.

We propose to adapt the power planning process and the 2017 Planning Law decrees to technological change in the electricity sector. Nowadays solar farms can be built in 18 months. Buildings and neighborhoods can be energy-positive. The PDP8 should include integrated grid and resource planning.

We propose that flexibility should be the priority goal for the “vision to 2040” part of the PDP8. Three points need immediate attention:

1. Design new thermal power plants not for baseload, but to be operated flexibly post 2030, including the possibility to co-fire biomass at high ratios.
 2. Better consider the options to integrate Vietnam with its electric neighbors (Laos, Cambodia Southern China). Besides providing interconnected countries flexibility to integrate renewable sources, the regional grid would also help to meet the electricity demand and reduce cost of building energy infrastructures. Development of the ASEAN regional grid has been discussed but the progress to establish one is slow. It is a reason to start acting on it soon with a focus on continental South-East Asia (Vietnam, Laos, Thailand, Cambodia, Myanmar, Southern China).
 3. Feasibility studies show that pumped storage power plants in the south and central regions could have a role to play in the vision to 2040 of the power system. More detailed cost-benefit analysis are required before turning this vision into a reality.
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Insight 6

Power market reforms are necessary to attract investment in additional capacity, and private capital prefer renewables

Power market reforms commingle two different projects. One is the corporate restructuring of EVN, the historical integrated electricity company. The other is the introduction of competition in electricity markets operations.

EVN has been structured into a number of companies for generation, transmission, distribution and services activities. This corporate restructuring takes place within a general policy of divestment from State owned enterprises. The policy aims to increase the efficiency of the economy by having these companies managed like private businesses, and to raise capital by selling part or all of their shares to the public. The fourth industrial revolution impacts the electricity sector, as technology allows decentralized production and storage, real time management, smarter appliances, and a new demand segment from electric vehicles. The State has a role to play in the electricity sector, if only because it is strategic to the national interest. But in a time of disruptive innovation, historical players without agency to rethink their business model head into trouble.

EVN cannot by itself realize all the investments necessary to follow up the demand increase. System expansion requires several billions dollars per year. Public debt is now much more difficult to access. The low demand for shares of Generation Company number 3 in its 2018 public offering somewhat chilled the capital-raising ambitions.

Opening the electricity markets is a way to attract other players, who can realize the investments. The introduction of competition in electricity markets operations is proceeding according to Decision 63/2013/QĐ-Ttg of the Prime Minister. First, a competitive generation electricity market was introduced in 2012. As of 2018, it comprises about half of the power plants in Vietnam. The introduction of competition in power generation has given power generation plants incentives to reduce their production costs and to develop a proper price offer strategy in the electricity market. The second phase, open since January 2019, is the wholesale electricity market involving the possibility of bilateral contracts between generators and resellers. Figure 4 shows the wholesale market price of electricity published hourly by National Load Dispatch Center. Solar and wind are not dispatched competitively, EVN has to buy all their production at a fixed price.

Figure 4. The intraday hourly load curve and wholesale market price on Tuesday, 30 July 2019 published by National Load Dispatch Center on www.nldc.evn.vn. The Vietnam wholesale electricity market (VWEM) has been operated since January 2019. The power market reforms are being implemented.

The next phase of the reform is to open the retail electricity market. In this stage, the EVN monopoly on distribution is dissolved. Direct Power Purchase Agreements (DPPA) between final customers and producers become possible. Many international socially responsible corporations are now committed to exclusively use renewable energy sources. Those operating in Vietnam, Heineken for example, are looking forward to be allowed to purchase power directly from solar and wind farms. Even without corporate responsibility objectives, where big rooftop space or large unused land nearby is available, it can be interesting for a Southern company to produce some of its own electricity or buy it from a solar farm, when it allows to avoid paying peak hour prices in the afternoon (Brohm, 2016). While it is actively desired by many companies, the DPPA model does not work in Vietnam yet.

We propose that the Electricity Law should be revised to separate Transmission and Distribution billing and more generally facilitate DPPA adoption.

We propose that international experience be used to find formulas for transmission and distribution fees with fair consequences for the various players including EVN, and recourse clauses that the standard DPPA contract should include for the case when the supplier does not meet its obligations.

Insight 7

Power from gas is cleaner but does not resolve the energy security issue

As Figure 1 shows, Vietnam already has gas power plants (Phu My, Ca Mau and Nhon Trach). While few new gas power plants opened between 2010 and 2020, much more action is expected in the next decade. Recent reviews of the PDP7 progress shows that between 2023 and 2028, 9 GW of new generation capacity from natural gas is expected to open (O Mon, Dung Quat, Mien Trung, Son My and Nhon Trach power stations). The role of natural gas in PDP8 could be even greater, as many other power generation projects have recently declared their intention to switch from coal to gas, from the modest Phu Quoc and Hoa Dau Long projects, to the large Long An projects. Investors have proposed to build LNG electricity plants in Vietnam. Some of the chosen locations are Ca Na (Ninh Thuan province) as well as Bac Lieu and Long Son (Ba Ria-Vung Tau province). However, the cost situation for both domestic and imported gas is highly uncertain.

Gas for O Mon (and later Kien Giang) power plant is to be sourced from offshore field Block B. The project implementation is facing many difficulties. Gas for the Mien Trung and Dung Quat plants is to be sourced domestically from the Blue Whale field. Its Final Investment Decision is targeted by 2020. That project is interesting because of the dispute over the right for exploitation between countries, and Vietnam halted one offshore natural gas project – Red Emperor – in the area in 2018.

Vietnam seeks to enter international market of liquid natural gas trade as a buyer. This market is growing. The balance between supply and demand shifts all the time. The United States is expanding its facilities to join Qatar, Australia and Malaysia in the top exporters club. Asia and Europe lead demand growth, with Japan, China and South Korea as top importers. It is impossible to predict where the gas prices will be in three years. It is certain however that the pricing volatility of fossil fuels is high – year-to-year doubling has been seen. Gas does not solve the energy security problem, only renewable energy sources do.

Finance, regulations from the government, and past trajectories determine the profitability of energy sources as much as than technology and market prices. In 2010-2020, the price of domestic coal was low, taxes on natural gas high, and there was no regasification infrastructures: coal was the cheapest. As investors move in an environment where environmental standards are very strict, access to capital for coal is restricted and electricity markets rewards flexibility, the balance tilts towards gas. Gas is cleaner a flexibility provider, but it still has CO₂ emissions.

We propose to build up the energy/macro-economy modeling and analysis capacity in Vietnam, to better understand (a) the implications of alternative coal/gas/renewable power mixes on the energy security situation and economic risks of fossil fuel dependency and (b) the implications of various royalties, duties, taxes, price regulations and cross subsidies schemes for domestic and imported fossil fuels and CO₂ emissions.

We propose to conduct a technology assessment of the floating storage and regasification units technology in Vietnam, to clarify (a) how, when and at which cost they could be used, (b) the perspectives of coupling these units with floating power barges, and (c) the conditions of arbitrage with land-based installations.

A large white wind turbine stands on a long pier extending into the sea. The sky is a clear, vibrant blue. In the background, another wind turbine is visible. A group of people is gathered on the pier near the base of the turbine. The overall scene is bright and clear, suggesting a sunny day.

The question is not IF solar and wind energy will develop in Vietnam, but HOW FAST and AT WHAT COST.

Towards a new energy narrative

The energy transition implies a new state of mind in the industry, which is difficult to reach after decades of putting the development of fossil fuels or nuclear as a first policy priority. However, the question is not IF solar and wind energy will develop in Vietnam, but HOW FAST and AT WHAT COST. Sooner or later, Vietnam will partake in the global energy transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy. This has started, year 2018 was a landmark “sun rush”. Will what follows be fast enough to avoid unacceptable local environmental pressure, meet the energy demand and achieve the nationally determined climate protection goals?

The booming of solar and wind energy projects is only one aspect of the energy transition, which is a system-wide change from centralized to decentralized. Everywhere, energy policies are considering a great emphasis on energy efficiency; the development of electromobility; and a smarter, more distributed management of the electricity network. The paradigm change has started in Vietnam. The Vietnam Initiative for the Energy Transition aims to switch the dominant discourse from:

Building more coal power plants will allow to satisfy the rapidly increasing power demand. Grid expands to transmit power from a small number of big power plants to everybody in the country.

To:

Focus is on renewable energy sources because they are domestic, affordable and quick to build. They will be distributed across the country, and now is the time to build the storage and smart grid to integrate them. It does not make economic sense to build new coal power plants, and gas does not solve the energy security issue.

The international environment has a role in Vietnam's technology choices. Developed countries took the lead in installing PV and wind farms, which led to cost decline and the present affordability. The development of non-conventional gas extraction technology activated the LNG position as an alternative to coal. International climate policy has carrots – technical assistance for renewable energy abounds – and sticks – coal finance is hard to get nowadays. However, all the propositions contained in this report can be acted on domestically. At VIETSE, we look forward to it.

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